

Electronic Supplementary Material for
Heterochrony and parallel evolution
of echinoderm, hemichordate and
cephalochordate internal bars

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Supplementary Fig. S1	1
Supplementary Fig. S2	2
Supplementary Fig. S3	4
Supplementary Fig. S4	5
Supplementary Fig. S5	6
Supplementary Table S1	7
Supplementary Table S2	8
Supplementary Table S3	10
Supplementary Text	11
Material and Methods	11
Samples	11
Three-dimensional reconstructions	11
Terminology	13
Measurement acquisitions	14
Data analysis	16
Results	16
Anatomical description	16
Comparisons with previous data	21
Statistical analyses	21
References	24
R script	27

Supplementary Fig. S1. Visualization of length, width, depth and spacing measurement acquisition from internal bars and bar-like structures in modern and fossil deuterostomes. a Stylophora. b Hemichordata and Cephalochordata. c–d Blastoidea. e–f Rhombifera.

Supplementary Fig. S2. Caption overleaf.

Supplementary Fig. S2 (previous page). Three-dimensional reconstructions of specimens (white) and internal bars and bar-like structures (violet) in modern and fossil deuterostomes. a–c Stylophora: a *Lagynocystis pyramidalis* (NHMUK E16107); b *Lagynocystis pyramidalis* (NHMUK E29453); c *Jaekelocarpus oklahomensis* (UWBM74305). d–e Blastoidea: d *Cryptoschisma* sp. (MGM-3383D); e *Hyperoblastus reimanni* (CMC IP 37404). f Rhombifera: *Strobilocystites polleyi* (CMC IP 36209). g–h Hemichordata: g *Balanoglossus* sp.; h *Schizocardium* sp. i Cephalochordata: *Branchiostoma floridae*. Scale bars are 1 mm.

Supplementary Fig. S3. Squared cosines of principal component analysis and their input to the first and second dimensions.

Supplementary Fig. S4. Boxplots representing morphological characteristics of the internal bars and bar-like structures in modern and fossil deuterostomes. a Length of bars and bar-like structures plotted against the total diameter of the pharynx/theca. **b** Width of bars and bar-like structures plotted against the total length of the pharynx/theca. **c** Depth of bars and bar-like structures plotted against the total length of the pharynx/theca. **d** Spacing of bars and bar-like structures plotted against the total length of the pharynx/theca (**a–b** and **d**, see **c** for key).

Supplementary Fig. S5. Linear discriminant analysis partition plots and apparent error rates. **a** Length against width of bars and bar-like structures. **b** Length against depth of bars and bar-like structures. **c** Width against depth of bars and bar-like structures. **d** Length against spacing of bars and bar-like structures. **e** Width against spacing of bars and bar-like structures. **f** Depth against spacing of bars and bar-like structures. Coloured regions delineate classification areas; the observations that fall within the correspondent region and therefore predicted to belong to that specific grouping are coloured black, the observations that fall outside of the predicted region are coloured red. B, Blastoidea (pink); C, Cephalochordata (yellow); H, Hemichordata (purple); R, Rhombifera (blue); S, Stylophora (orange). (**a–d** and **f**, see **e** for key).

species	collection number	scanner	voltage (kV)	current (uA)	filter type	filter thickness	exposure time (ms)	projections
<i>Lagynocystis pyramidalis</i>	NHMUK E29453 a_b	Nikon Metrology HMX ST 225, NHM	180	95	copper	0.5	708	3142
<i>Lagynocystis pyramidalis</i>	NHMUK E29454 c	Nikon Metrology HMX ST 226, NHM	180	170	copper	0.25	708	3142
<i>Lagynocystis pyramidalis</i>	NHMUK E16107	Nikon Metrology HMX ST 226, NHM	180	95	copper	0.5	708	3142
<i>Lagynocystis pyramidalis</i>	NHMUK E29043	Nikon Metrology HMX ST 227, NHM	180	95	copper	0.5	708	3142
<i>Jaekelocarpus oklahomensis</i>	UWBM 74305	University of texas High resolution X-ray facility	150	53	no filter	no filter	?	1800
<i>Strobilocystites polleyi</i>	CMC IP 36209	Nikon Metrology HMX ST 225, NHM	170	160	no filter	no filter	2000	3600
<i>Balanoglossus</i> sp.		Nikon Metrology HMX ST 225, NHM	150	140	no filter	no filter	500	3142
<i>Schizocardium</i> sp.		Nikon Metrology HMX ST 225, NHM	150	125	no filter	no filter	500	3142
<i>Branchiostoma floridae</i>		Nikon Metrology HMX ST 225, NHM	150	140	no filter	no filter	500	3142

species	collection number	scanner	energy (keV)	sample to detector distance	exposure time (ms)	projections
<i>Cryptoschisma</i> sp.	MGM-3383D	TOMCAT-Xo2DA, Paul Scherrer Institut	37	350	900	1201
<i>Hyperblastus reimanni</i>	CMC IP 37404	TOMCAT-Xo2DA, Paul Scherrer Institut	37	350	1000	1001

Supplementary Table S1. Settings used in X-ray microtomography and synchrotron tomography scans of modern and fossil deuterostomes.

species	Taxonomical grouping	Length (mm)					Width (mm)					Depth (mm)					Spacing (mm)			Pharynx/Theca (mm)		# data points		
		min	max	mean	stdev	median	min	max	mean	stdev	median	min	max	mean	stdev	median	min	max	mean	stdev	median		length	width
<i>Lagynocystis pyramidalis</i>	Stylophora	0.140	1.280	0.711	0.270	0.725	0.060	0.190	0.121	0.031	0.118	0.050	0.270	0.144	0.044	0.138	0.030	0.160	0.086	0.030	0.090	12.5	5.0	42
<i>Jaekelocarpus oklahomensis</i>	Stylophora	0.290	0.820	0.564	0.167	0.580	0.080	0.120	0.099	0.014	0.095	0.200	0.400	0.303	0.064	0.300	0.080	0.170	0.104	0.028	0.100	3.9	3.5	8
<i>Balanoglossus</i> sp.	Hemichordata	1.350	3.150	2.458	0.392	2.465	0.060	0.090	0.068	0.009	0.066	0.065	0.120	0.093	0.013	0.091	0.050	0.150	0.093	0.026	0.090	70.0	3.0	20
<i>Schizocardium</i> sp.	Hemichordata	0.900	2.050	1.656	0.346	1.800	0.040	0.070	0.053	0.007	0.050	0.070	0.150	0.112	0.021	0.110	0.060	0.110	0.084	0.017	0.088	16.0	1.5	30
<i>Branchiostoma floridae</i>	Cephalochordata	1.900	2.950	2.515	0.232	2.500	0.035	0.055	0.041	0.005	0.040	0.015	0.025	0.021	0.002	0.021	0.040	0.055	0.044	0.005	0.040	26.0	2.2	30
<i>Cryptoschisma</i> sp.	Blastoidea	0.900	2.700	1.673	0.493	1.650	0.060	0.130	0.096	0.020	0.100	0.500	1.310	0.978	0.284	1.100	0.060	0.130	0.094	0.020	0.100	3.1	6.3	16
<i>Hyperblastus reimanni</i>	Blastoidea	1.600	2.500	2.004	0.309	2.100	0.180	0.230	0.200	0.016	0.200	0.450	0.700	0.538	0.073	0.510	0.240	0.350	0.281	0.032	0.270	4.0	5.2	9
<i>Strobilocystites polleyi</i>	Rhombifera	0.230	0.890	0.531	0.156	0.550	0.100	0.230	0.167	0.032	0.160	1.900	3.700	2.645	0.443	2.600	0.090	0.210	0.148	0.030	0.150	2.3	2.1	69

Supplementary Table S2 (previous page). Length, width, depth and spacing measurements of internal bars and bar-like structures in modern and fossil deuterostomes.

Length	B.f	B.sp	C.sp	H.r	J.o	L.p1	L.p2	St.sp	Length	B	C	H	R
B.sp	0.000								C	0.000			
C.sp	0.000	0.000							H	0.000	0.001		
H.r	0.000	0.000	1.000						R	0.000	0.000	0.000	
J.o	0.101	0.000	0.000	0.000					S	0.000	0.000	1.000	0.000
L.p1	0.000	0.003	0.000	0.000	0.000								
L.p2	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.000							
S.p	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.002	0.000	0.000						
S.sp	1.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.322	0.000	0.000	0.000					

Width	B.f	B.sp	C.sp	H.r	J.o	L.p1	L.p2	St.sp	Width	B	C	H	R
B.sp	0.016								C	1.000			
C.sp	0.003	0.000							H	0.000	0.000		
H.r	0.000	0.000	0.000						R	0.000	0.000	0.000	
J.o	0.000	0.191	0.000	0.018					S	0.387	0.001	0.001	0.000
L.p1	0.005	1.000	0.000	0.000	0.124								
L.p2	0.000	1.000	0.000	0.000	1.000	1.000							
S.p	0.000												
S.sp	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.000	0.082	0.000	0.000	0.000					

Depth	B.f	B.sp	C.sp	H.r	J.o	L.p1	L.p2	St.sp	Depth	B	C	H	R
B.sp	0.000								C	0.000			
C.sp	0.000	0.000							H	0.000	0.000		
H.r	0.000	0.000	0.01						R	0.000	0.000	0.000	
J.o	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.000					S	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
L.p1	0.000	1.000	0.000	0.000	0.000								
L.p2	0.000	0.068	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.366							
S.p	0.000												
S.sp	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.002	1.000	0.000	0.000	0.000					

Spacing	B.f	B.sp	C.sp	H.r	J.o	L.p1	L.p2	St.sp	Spacing	B	C	H	R
B.sp	0.000								C	0.950			
C.sp	0.001	0.000							H	0.000	0.000		
H.r	0.000	0.000	0.000						R	0.000	0.000	0.000	
J.o	0.002	1.000	0.000	0.000					S	0.020	1.000	0.000	0.000
L.p1	1.000	0.000	0.019	0.000	0.000								
L.p2	0.000	0.000	0.215	0.000	0.000	0.000							
S.p	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.091	0.000	0.000	0.000						
S.sp	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001					

Supplementary Table S3: Analysis of variance results with Bonferroni correction

of standard deviations at species and higher taxonomical group levels. Bold

indicates a statistically significant result where the null hypothesis is rejected.

Abbreviations as per captions to Figure 2 and Supplementary Figure S4.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Samples

Fossils of *L. pyramidalis* were originally collected from the Šárka Formation (Darriwilian), Czechia. The original skeletons of *L. pyramidalis* samples were dissolved during diagenesis and preserved in three dimensions as uncompressed, articulated moulds in siliceous nodules, which had previously been split for study. The specimen of *J. oklahomensis* (UWBM 74305) is housed in the Thomas Burke Memorial Washington State Museum. This fossil is three-dimensionally preserved as recrystallised calcite, and comes from the upper Carboniferous (Pennsylvanian) Gene Autry Shale Formation (Pennsylvanian) of Oklahoma, USA [1]. Specimens of extant enteropneusts and the cephalochordate were stained with phosphotungstic acid for 17 days to enhance the contrast between the collagen in the gill bars and the surrounding tissues [2]. Fossil blastozoans are three-dimensionally preserved as recrystallised calcite infilled with sediment; in *H. reimanni*, elements of the internal anatomy have been replaced with pyrite.

Three-dimensional reconstructions

Three-dimensional reconstruction of *L. pyramidalis* (exterior; NHMUK E29453 a_b) was obtained from 546 slices with an inverted linear threshold generation of 113. Three-dimensional reconstruction of *L. pyramidalis* c (interior; NHMUK E29453 c) was obtained from 1848 slices with an inverted linear threshold generation of 335 individual slices were despeckled prior to reconstruction. The two reconstructions of *L. pyramidalis* (NHMUK E29453 a_b and E29453 c) were digitally combined in SPIERSview using the “pieces panel”. Three-dimensional reconstruction of *L. pyramidalis* (NHMUK E16107) was obtained from 973 slices with a generated range

of three thresholds (threshold 1, 0–48; threshold 2, 38–181; threshold 3, 181–255), individual slices were despeckled prior reconstruction. Three-dimensional reconstruction of *L. pyramidalis* (NHMUK E29043) was obtained from 1141 slices with a generated range of two thresholds (threshold 1, 0–52; threshold 2, 221–255). *J. oklahomensis* was obtained from 276 slices with a generated range of two thresholds (threshold 1, 84–179; threshold 2, 179–255), individual slices were adjusted for contrast and brightness prior reconstruction.

The reconstruction of *Cryptoschisma* sp. (MGM-3383D) was obtained from 489 slices with a generated range of three thresholds (threshold 1, 25–43; threshold 2, 43–44; threshold 3, 43–255), a medium filter of 1x1 pixel was applied to all slices prior to reconstruction. *H. reimanni* (CMP IP 37404) was obtained from 2480 slices with a generated range of four thresholds (threshold 1, 60–82; threshold 2, 82–120; threshold 3, 120–144; threshold 4, 144–255) and down sampling value in axes X, Y and Z of 2.

Three dimensional reconstruction of *S. polleyi* (CMC IP 36209) was obtained from 1740 slices with a generated range of three thresholds (threshold 1, 38–120; threshold 2, 120–155; threshold 3, 155–255) and down sampling value in axes X, Y and Z of 2.

Three-dimensional reconstruction of *Schizocardium* sp. was generated from 1876 slices with a generated range of two thresholds (threshold 1, 36–181; threshold 2, 164–255), individual slices were despeckled prior to reconstruction. *Balanoglossus* sp. was scanned doubly as a full body length scan did not obtain enough resolution for the reconstruction of pharyngeal bars. Full body *Balanoglossus* sp. three-dimensional reconstruction was obtained from 1999 slices with a linear threshold generation value of 60 and down sampling value in axes X, Y, Z of 2. *Balanoglossus* sp. pharynx

three-dimensional reconstruction was obtained from 1844 slices with a generated range of three thresholds (threshold 1, 41–96; threshold 2, 100–191; threshold 3, 174–255), individual slices were despeckled prior reconstruction. *B. floridae* was also scanned doubly as a full body length scan did not obtain enough resolution for the reconstruction of pharyngeal bars. Full body *B. floridae* three-dimensional reconstruction was obtained from 1861 slices with a generated range of three thresholds (threshold 1, 51–105; threshold 2, 105–174; threshold 3, 17–246) and a down sampling value in axes X, Y and Z of 2, individual slices were despeckled prior to reconstruction. The pharynx area of *B. floridae* was obtained from 1910 slices with a generated range of four thresholds (threshold 1, 43–80; threshold 2, 80–138; threshold 3, 138–220; threshold 4, 211–255) and down sampling value in axes X, Y and Z of 2, individual slices were despeckled prior to reconstruction.

Terminology

Terms used in the main text and throughout the supplementary text are defined as follows: “pharyngeal gill bars” and “gill bars” refer to the collagenous, elongated internal structures found in the pharynges of some modern deuterostomes; “pharyngeal openings” refers to the outlets in the pharynges, which are surrounded by the collagenous gill bars in some modern deuterostomes; “internal bars” refers to calcified, elongated bars found in the internal body chamber (or theca) of the stylophorans *J. oklahomensis* and *L. pyramidalis*; “internal bar-like structures” refers to the calcified folds in fossil blastoids and pores in fossil rhombiferans both presumably functioning in respiration.

Measurement acquisitions

Measurements of bars length, width, depth and spacing were acquired using SPIERSview. Orientation of *Schizocardium* sp., *Balanoglossus* sp., *B. floridae*, *Cryptoschisma* sp, *H. reimanni* and *S. polleyi* follow conventional agreement; for example, for blastoids we follow [3], hemichordates [4], and the cephalochordate [5]. Orientation of *L. pyramidalis* follows [6] and *J. oklahomensis* [7].

Bar Length. Measured following the upper, median line from the first appearance of the bar to its disappearance. In *L. pyramidalis*, length of bar structures was measured from its appearance from the internal wall at the dorsal side of the theca to their disappearance (Supplementary Fig. S1a). In *J. oklahomensis*, length of bar structures was measured from its appearance from the internal wall at each side of the theca to their disappearance in the central cavity (Supplementary Fig. S1a). In *Cryptoschisma* sp. and *H. reimanni* the length of individual bars of the hydrospires structures was measured from their appearance at the oral surface to their disappearance at the aboral end of the theca (Supplementary Fig. S1c). In *S. polleyi*, length of the inter-pore walls was measured from the top-most surface of the plate to their disappearance internally at the thecal cavity (Supplementary Fig. S1e). In *Balanoglossus* sp. and *Schizocardium* sp., bar length was measured from its appearance at the endostyle to their disappearance at the epibranchial groove (digitally removed) (Supplementary Fig. S1b). In *B. floridae*, bar length was measured from the endostyle to the bar's disappearance at the dorsal area (Supplementary Fig. S1b).

Bar width. Measured from left end to right end of each bar in *L. pyramidalis*, *J. oklahomensis*, *Cryptoschisma* sp. and *H. reimanni* from an oral view (Supplementary Fig. S1a, c). In *S. polleyi*, bar width was measured from wall to wall

on the shortest axis of each oval-shaped pore opening from a perpendicular view of the external surface (Supplementary Fig. S1e). Measured from the anterior end to the posterior end of each bar in *Balanoglossus* sp., *Schizocardium* sp. and *B. floridae* while looking laterally to the pharynx (Supplementary Fig. S1b).

Bar depth. Measured from the body wall towards the central axis of the theca on each bar-like structure in *L. pyramidalis* and *J. oklahomensis* (Supplementary Fig. S1a). In *Cryptoschisma* sp. and *H. reimanni* was measured from the body wall towards the central axis of the theca (Supplementary Fig. S1d). In *S. polleyi*, was measured from the pore opening at the plate's surface to its disappearance in the thecal cavity (Supplementary Fig. S1f). Measured from the upper, median line of each crest to the lower, median line of its consecutive trough in *Balanoglossus* sp., *Schizocardium* sp. and *B. floridae* while looking dorsally the pharynx (Supplementary Fig. S1b). For this measurement, SPIERSview was placed on “clipping panel” option; it permits to digitally remove entire regions of the three-dimensional reconstruction without altering the proportions.

Bar spacing. In *L. pyramidalis*, *Cryptoschisma* sp. and *H. reimanni* bar spacing was measured from the left-most end of each bar to the right-most end of that same bar (Supplementary Fig. S1a, c). In *S. polleyi*, it was measured from the boundary of each inter-pore opening to the closest boundary of the next opening from a 90° view of the external surface (Supplementary Fig. S1e). In *Balanoglossus* sp., *Schizocardium* sp. and *B. floridae* it was measured from the posterior end of each bar to the anterior end of the next consecutive bar while looking laterally to the pharynx (Supplementary Fig. S1b).

Data analysis

Principal component analysis (PCA), which entails an orthogonal linear transformation of the data into a new coordinate system, such that the variance of the data is projected in different components independently of designated classes. Linear discriminant analysis (LDA), which reduces the dimensions of multivariate data into linear combinations based on designated classes, in this case taxonomic groupings.

RESULTS

Anatomical description

Lagynocystis pyramidalis (Stylophora, Echinodermata). Our digital reconstructions show the same external anatomy as described by previous authors [6, 8–10] (Fig. 1a and Supplementary Fig. S2a, b). The best preserved external morphology was found in NHMUK E29043 (Fig. 1a). The posterior side of the theca is overlaid by a large plate, slightly resembling a trapezoid, covering the immediate anterior part to the appendage's attachment (Fig. 1a and Supplementary Fig. S2a, b). The best-preserved internal bars were found in NHMUK E16107 (Fig. 1b and Supplementary Fig. S2a) where the original calcite was replaced with pyrite during diagenesis allowing for an exceptional preservation of the internal bars. Bars decrease in length from the centre to the laterals on the side complexes while the central complex encloses a larger central bar surrounded by two shorter bars on each side (Fig. 2b). The remaining of the plates were not preserved or were not visualised in the scans. The upper side of the theca is composed of two large triangular plates situated posteriorly, one small, slightly circular plate in the central part of the body, another two triangular plates anteriorly and a highly acute triangular plate forms the anterior-most part of the theca (Fig. 1a and Supplementary Fig. S2a, b). The appendage is composed of three parts; anteriorly is thick and ornamented with robust spines, centrally is thinner and spines

are smaller, posteriorly is not greatly preserved, yet appears to be slender and smooth (Fig. 1a and Supplementary Fig. S2a, b). The interior of the theca houses a series of repeating elongate bars, which are divided into three elliptical fields, one median and two lateral; each field attaches to the inner surface of a different thecal plate (located adjacent to the insertion of the main appendage). There are at least 25 bars distributed over the three fields; five bars in the central field and around 10 bars in each of the two lateral fields (Fig. 1b). Several bars appear to have been lost due to post-depositional deformation (Fig. 1b and Supplementary Fig. S2a, b), particularly in NHMUK E29453 (Supplementary Fig. S2b), which was therefore excluded from the statistical analyses. In the two other specimens, bar length varies from 0.140–1.280 mm, with the longest bars situated in the central field (Fig. 2b and Supplementary Table S2). The width, depth and spacing of the bars are fairly consistent among the two lateral and central fields, averaging 0.121 mm, 0.144 mm and 0.086 mm, respectively (Supplementary Table S2).

Jaekelocarpus oklahomensis (Stylophora, Echinodermata). Skeletal characters recognised in the novel reconstruction of *J. oklahomensis* are comparable to those described previously from the same specimen: dorsally flatten and ventrally convex theca formed by ten plates, 3 plates positioned ventrally, 4 external and 3 internal plates dorsally (Supplementary Fig. S2c and [7]). The thecal cavity houses two bilaterally symmetrical complexes of internal bars, each of which comprises four elongate bars arising from the internal wall of the adjacent thecal plate projecting towards the centre of the theca (Supplementary Fig. S2c). Bar length varies from 0.290 mm to 0.820 mm; the longest bars are situated close to the flat thecal surface, with bar length decreasing towards the opposing (convex) surface of the theca (Supplementary Fig. S2c and Supplementary Table S2). The width, depth and spacing

of the bars are fairly consistent, averaging 0.099 mm, 0.303 mm and 0.104 mm, respectively (Supplementary Table S2).

Balanoglossus sp. (Enteropneusta, Hemichordata). At least 154 gill bars extend from immediately posterior of the collar to about one-third the length of the trunk, spanning across the pharyngeal wall (Supplementary Fig. S2g). The bars are arranged in pairs (Supplementary Fig. S2g). The length of the bars ranges from 3.150 mm at the posterior end of the pharynx to 1.350 mm at the anterior, with an average of 2.458 mm across the entire pharynx. The width, depth and spacing of the bars are approximately constant along the full length of the pharynx, averaging 0.068 mm, 0.093 mm and 0.093 mm, respectively (Supplementary Table S2).

Schizocardium sp. (Enteropneusta, Hemichordata). A minimum of 130 gill bars extend from immediately posterior of the collar to about three-quarters of the distance along the length of the trunk, occupying the entirety of the pharynx (Fig. 1e and Supplementary Fig. S2h). The bars are arranged in pairs with shorter primary bars followed by longer secondary bars that bifurcate ventrally (Supplementary Fig. S2h). The length of bars ranges between 0.900 mm at the posterior end of the pharynx to 2.050 mm at the centre, with an average of 1.656 mm for the entire pharynx. The width of the bars and the spacing between them do not vary substantially throughout the pharynx, averaging 0.053 mm and 0.084 mm, respectively. The depth of the bars reaches a maximum at the centre of the pharynx of 0.150 mm, with an average over the entire pharynx of 0.112 mm (Supplementary Table S2).

Additional structures identified in both hemichordate specimens include dorsal nerve cord, epibranchial groove, parabranial ridges, glomerulus, kidney, heart, stomochord, and possible gonads (Fig. 1e and Supplementary Fig. S2g, h).

Branchiostoma floridae (Cephalochordata, Chordata). At least 250 gill bars are housed inside the pharynx beginning immediately posterior of the mouth to about half the length of the body (Fig. 2f and Supplementary Fig. S2i). The bars are arranged in pairs with primary bars followed by secondary bars that bifurcate ventrally (Fig. 1f and Supplementary Fig. S2i). The length of the bars ranges from 1.900 mm at the anterior end of the pharynx to 2.950 mm at the centre, averaging 2.515 mm (Supplementary Table S2). The width and depth of the bars is about the same for the entire pharynx, with averages of 0.041 mm and 0.021 mm, respectively (Supplementary Table S2). The spacing between the bars slightly increases posteriorly, with an average spacing of 0.040 mm at the anterior and 0.046 mm at the posterior end (Fig. 1f). Additional structures identified in the cephalochordate include notochord, myomeres, gonads and gill slit openings (Fig. 1f and Supplementary Fig. S2i).

Cryptoschisma sp. (Blastoidea, Echinodermata). Eight hydrospire groups are preserved in the theca (Fig. 1c and Supplementary Fig. S2d), with two absent in the C-D interray. A total of 42 well-preserved folds (bar-like elements of the respiratory system) are distributed across the eight hydrospire groups. These folds are vertically elongated and extend across almost the entire length of the thecal cavity. They are ellipsoidal with a rounded terminus (hydrospire tube) and usually arranged in groups of seven with some exceptions due to preservation (Supplementary Fig. S2d). The folds are connected to the exterior by elongate slits adjacent to the ambulacra [11]. The fold length varies from 0.500 mm to 1.950 mm from the sides to the centre of each of the groups (Fig. 1c, Supplementary Fig. S2d and Supplementary Table S2). The width and spacing of the folds are very similar throughout the specimen, with averages of 0.096 mm and 0.094 mm, respectively (Supplementary Table S2). The

depth of the folds is also fairly consistent with an average of 0.978 mm (Supplementary Table S2).

Hyperoblastus reimanni (Blastoidea, Echinodermata). Ten hydrospire groups, divided into five pairs are present within the theca (Supplementary Fig. S2e). The folds are vertically elongated, covering almost the entire length of the thecal cavity. There are 18 well-preserved folds distributed among the five hydrospire pairs (Supplementary Fig. S2e). The folds are connected to the exterior by sutural pores and slits along the ambulacra, with five round openings (spiracles) on the oral surface (covered by sediment in our specimen) [12]. The length of the folds varies from 1.600 mm in the centre to 2.500 mm at the sides of each of the hydrospire groups; the average fold length is 2.004 mm (Supplementary Table S2). The width and spacing of the folds are similar in each of the hydrospire groups, with averages of 0.077 mm and 0.103 mm, respectively (Supplementary Table S2). The depth of the folds is about 0.538 mm across all the hydrospire groups (Supplementary Table S2).

The blastoids contain five pairs of hydrospires, one in each ambulacrum acquiring 2–1–2 symmetry [13–15]. The calyx of *Cryptoschisma* sp. was scanned targeting exclusively the hydrospire structures, consequently external plates are not fully reconstructed (Fig. 1c and Supplementary Fig. S2d).

Strobilocystites polleyi (Rhombifera, Echinodermata). The theca contains three complexes of rhomb-pore (bar-like elements of the respiratory system) bearing structures (Fig. 1d) [16]. These oval-shaped pores perforate the thecal plates, connecting the interior to the exterior, and there is no evident connection of the three complexes to the mouth or ambulacra (Fig. 1d and Supplementary Fig. S2f). The number of visible openings varies across the complexes from 39 to 57 (Fig. 1d). The length of the pores varies somewhat throughout the specimen (0.230 mm–0.890 mm),

with an average of 0.531 mm (Supplementary Table S2). The width and spacing of the pores are more consistent, with averages of 0.167 mm and 0.148 mm, respectively (Supplementary Table S2). The depth of the pores varies, with the deeper pores located in the centre of the complex and an average of 2.645 mm across all the pores (Supplementary Table S2).

Comparisons with previous data

Our measurements (Table 1) coincide with measurements acquired in previous studies of the morphological characteristics of pharyngeal bars in modern cephalochordates [17] and hemichordates [18], folds of the hydrospires system in blastoids [19] and pore structures in cystoids [20].

Statistical analyses

In LDA, the first and second discriminants account for 98.08% of the variability in the data (Fig. 2a, c). In PCA, the first and second components account for 91.2% of the variation (Fig. 2b, d). In PCA, all the components have a large input (Fig. 2d and Supplementary Fig. S3), while in LDA, the length, width and spacing accounted for successively smaller portions of the observed variability (Fig. 2c and Supplementary Fig. S5). The great majority of the variability in the data is explained by the length and depth in both LDA and PCA (Fig. 2c, d, Supplementary Figs. S3 and S5b).

Results listed in the main text are confirmed by analysis of boxplots of the individual morphological characteristics (Supplementary Fig. S4). Length and depth show the largest variability among groups, congruently with standard deviation values (Supplementary Fig. S4a, c and Supplementary Table S2). Length of bars holds a strong correlation to the length of the pharynx in the cephalochordate and

hemichordates taxa or theca in echinoderms (Supplementary Fig. S4a); individual taxonomic groups show increasing length of bars and bar-like structures as the length of the pharynx or theca increases. Similarly, width of bars shows a strong correlation to the circumference of the pharynx/theca in hemichordates and stylophorans (Supplementary Fig. S4b). Bar depth and spacing, do not seem to be correlated to the dimensions of the pharynx/theca (Supplementary Fig. S4c, d).

Interrogation of LDA through partition plots of pairs of discriminants shows that the pairing of length and depth produces the smallest error rate in the data (12.1%) and the fewer observations fall outside of their predicted region (Supplementary Fig. S5b), these are predominantly stylophorans observations falling on the hemichordates classification area and vice versa. Opposing, the largest error rate is produced by the pairing of width and spacing (25.4%) and the largest number of observations fall outside of their predicted region (Supplementary Fig. S5e). The blastoids and rhombiferan predominantly plot in their classification area of the morphospace (e.g. Supplementary Fig. S5b); however, when blastoid observations are projected outside of the predicted region are usually plotted in the rhombiferan classification area (Supplementary Fig. S5a, d). In all cases, the grouping Stylophora, Hemichordata and Cephalochordata houses the majority of the observations falling outside of their correspondent classification areas but doing so within the predicted regions of other components of this group (Supplementary Fig. S5).

MANOVA of the internal bars in the stylophorans, enteropneusts and cephalochordate and the bar-like elements of the respiratory system in the blastoids and rhombiferan reveal that there are statistically significant differences between individual groups ($F(68.70) = 2.226, p < 2.2e-16$) and species ($F(72.87) = 2.922, p < 2.2e-16$) for all the measured variables.

ANOVA of individual species demonstrates that in terms of the length of the bars, *J. oklahomensis*, *B. floridae* and *Schizocardium* sp. show no statistically significant differences (Supplementary Table S3).

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R script

```
library(ggplot2)
library(magrittr)
library(ggpubr)
library(nlme)
library(rpart)
library(factoextra)
library(spatstat.data)
library(spatstat)
library(MASS)
library(klaR)

# Call the data (taxon/position)
setwd("/Users/aidin_13_/Desktop/gillslit/data/newdata/newdata")
data<-read.csv("gill_data_new_results_stand25.csv", header=T)
data

# Density is the first check

ggdensity(data$Length.stand, ylab = "Density of length", xlab = "Length")
ggdensity(data$Width.stand, ylab = "Density of width", xlab = "Width")
ggdensity(data$Depth.stand, ylab = "Density of depth", xlab = "Depth")
ggdensity(data$Spacing.stand, ylab = "Density of spacing", xlab = "Spacing")

hist(data$Length.stand)
hist(data$Width.stand)
hist(data$Depth.stand)
hist(data$Spacing.stand)

# Quantile - Quantile plot correlation between a given sample and the normal
distribution.
ggqqplot(data$Length.stand)
ggqqplot(data$Width.stand)
ggqqplot(data$Depth.stand)
ggqqplot(data$Spacing.stand)

# Shapiro Normality test if p-value >0.05 the distribution of the data are not
significantly different from normal distribution, we can assume normality.
shapiro.test(data$Length.stand)
shapiro.test(data$Width.stand)
shapiro.test(data$Depth.stand)
shapiro.test(data$Spacing.stand)

# Boxplot (To investigate the distribution of the data)
boxplot(data[,7:10])

# Vectors
sp <- data$species
sp <- as.vector(sp)
```

```

gr <- data$Group
gr <- as.vector(gr)

hex <- data$hex
hex <- as.vector(hex)

sp[which(sp == "Lagynocystis pyramidalis NHMUK E29453")] <-"L.p1"
sp[which(sp == "Lagynocystis pyramidalis NHMUK E16107")] <-"L.p2"
sp[which(sp == "Schizocardium sp.") <-"S.sp"
sp[which(sp == "Balanoglossus sp.") <-"B.sp"
sp[which(sp == "Branchiostoma floridae")] <-"B.f"
sp[which(sp == "Cryptoschisma sp.") <-"C.sp"
sp[which(sp == "Hyperoblastus reimanni")] <-"H.r"
sp[which(sp == "Strobilocystites sp.") <-"St.sp"
sp[which(sp == "Jaekelocarpus oklahomensis")] <-"J.o"

# Boxplot (To investigate the distribution of the data)
boxplot(data[,2:5])

#Boxplot bar length vs body length
boxplot(Length~Body.length, col=hex, data = data, main = ("pharynx/theca length vs
bar length"), xlab = "pharynx/theca length (mm)", ylab = "bar length (mm)")
legend(locator(1), c("Balanoglossus sp.", "Branchiostoma floridae", "Cryptoschisma
sp.", "Jaekelocarpus oklahomensis", "Lagynocystis pyramidalis 2", "Lagynocystis
pyramidalis 1", "Schizocardium sp.", "Hyperoblastus reimanni", "Strobilocystites
sp."), pch=19, col=c("#ff9900", "#ff4646", "#ab59bc", "#6682ff", "#66ccff",
"#ff66cc", "#99ffcc", "#cc9900", "#33cc33"),cex=2/3, bty = "n")

#Boxplot bar width vs body circumference
boxplot(Width~Body.circum, col=hex, data = data, main = ("pharynx/theca
circumference vs bar width"), xlab = "pharynx/theca circumference (mm)", ylab =
"bar width (mm)")
legend(locator(1), c("Balanoglossus sp.", "Branchiostoma floridae", "Cryptoschisma
sp.", "Jaekelocarpus oklahomensis", "Lagynocystis pyramidalis 2", "Lagynocystis
pyramidalis 1", "Schizocardium sp.", "Hyperoblastus reimanni", "Strobilocystites
sp."), pch=19, col=c("#ff9900", "#ff4646", "#ab59bc", "#6682ff", "#66ccff",
"#ff66cc", "#99ffcc", "#cc9900", "#33cc33"),cex=2/3, bty = "n")

#Boxplot bar depth vs body circumference
boxplot(Depth~Body.circum, col=hex, data = data, main = ("pharynx/theca
circumference vs bar depth"), xlab = "pharynx/theca circumference (mm)", ylab =
"bar depth (mm)")
legend(locator(1), c("Balanoglossus sp.", "Branchiostoma floridae", "Cryptoschisma
sp.", "Jaekelocarpus oklahomensis", "Lagynocystis pyramidalis 2", "Lagynocystis
pyramidalis 1", "Schizocardium sp.", "Hyperoblastus reimanni", "Strobilocystites
sp."), pch=19, col=c("#ff9900", "#ff4646", "#ab59bc", "#6682ff", "#66ccff",
"#ff66cc", "#99ffcc", "#cc9900", "#33cc33"),cex=2/3, bty = "n")

#Boxplot bar spacing vs body circumference
boxplot(Spacing~Body.circum, col=hex, data = data, main = ("pharynx/theca

```

```

circumference vs bar spacing"), xlab = "pharynx/theca circumference (mm)", ylab =
"bar spacing (mm)")
legend(locator(1), c("Balanoglossus sp.", "Branchiostoma floridae", "Cryptoschisma
sp.", "Jaekelocarpus oklahomensis", "Lagynocystis pyramidalis 2", "Lagynocystis
pyramidalis 1", "Schizocardium sp.", "Hyperoblastus reimanni", "Strobilocystites
sp."), pch=19, col=c("#ff9900", "#ff4646", "#ab59bc", "#6682ff", "#66ccff",
"#ff66cc", "#99ffcc", "#cc9900", "#33cc33"),cex=2/3, bty = "n")

datalog<- log(data[,7:10])
data$Length <- datalog[,1]
data$Width <- datalog[,2]
data$Depth <- datalog[,3]
data$Spacing <- datalog[,4]

# PCA log
pca <- prcomp(data [,2:5], scale = TRUE)
attach(pca)
prop.pca = pca$sdev^2 / sum(pca$sdev^2) # proportions
print (prop.pca)

# Plot scores
pcascores <- pca$x
plot(pcascores[,1:2],pch=19, col=c("red", "blue", "green", "orange"), xlab="PC1 -
72.90%", ylab="PC2 - 18.30%")

pcaloadings <- pca$rotation

plot(pcaloadings[,1:2], pch=19, col=c("red", "blue", "green", "orange"), xlab="PC1 -
72.90%", ylab="PC2 - 18.30%")
legend(locator(1), c("Length", "Width", "Depth", "Spacing"), pch=19, col=c("red",
"blue", "green", "orange"),cex=2/3, bty = "n")

plot(pcaloadings[,3:4], pch=19, col=c("red", "blue", "green", "orange"), xlab="PC1 -
6.24%", ylab="PC2 - 2.57%")
legend(locator(1), c("Length", "Width", "Depth", "Spacing"), pch=19, col=c("red",
"blue", "green", "orange"),cex=2/3, bty = "n")

# Eigen values for PCA
eig <- get_eigenvalue(pca)
eig
fviz_eig(pca, addlabels = TRUE) # plot

# Results vor variables
var <- get_pca_var(pca)
var
fviz_cos2(pca, choice = "var") # plot dimension 1
fviz_cos2(pca, choice = "var", axes = 1:2) # plot dimensions 1 and 2

head (var$cos2, 4)

```

```

# Quality factor map with cos2 colours
fviz_pca_var(pca, col.var = "cos2", gradient.cols = c("#00AFBB", "#E7B800",
"#FC4E07"))

# plot PCA
plot(pca$x[,1:2], col=hex, pch= 19, xlab="PC1 - 72.90%", ylab="PC2 - 18.30%")
legend(locator(1), c("Balanoglossus sp.", "Branchiostoma floridae", "Cryptoschisma
sp.", "Jaekelocarpus oklahomensis", "Lagynocystis pyramidalis 2", "Lagynocystis
pyramidalis 1", "Schizocardium sp.", "Hyperoblastus reimanni", "Strobilocystites
sp."), pch=19, col=c("#ff9900", "#ff4646", "#ab59bc", "#6682ff", "#66ccff",
"#ff66cc", "#99ffcc", "#cc9900", "#33cc33"),cex=2/3, bty = "n")
text(x[,1],x[,2], labels = sp, col=hex, cex=0.5, pos=3)

# Plot Group
levelPlot <- levels(gr)[1]
levelPlot # this will plot Blastoidea
rowNums <- which(gr == levelPlot)
hpts<- convexhull.xy(x[rowNums,1:2])
hpts$bdry[[1]]$x
polygon(hpts$bdry[[1]]$x, hpts$bdry[[1]]$y, col="#f75d7c50")

levelPlot <- levels(gr)[2]
levelPlot # this will plot Cephalochordate
rowNums <- which(gr == levelPlot)
hpts<- convexhull.xy(x[rowNums,1:2])
hpts$bdry[[1]]$x
polygon(hpts$bdry[[1]]$x, hpts$bdry[[1]]$y, col="#e9e92750")

levelPlot <- levels(gr)[3]
levelPlot # this will plot Hemichordate
rowNums <- which(gr == levelPlot)
hpts<- convexhull.xy(x[rowNums,1:2])
hpts$bdry[[1]]$x
polygon(hpts$bdry[[1]]$x, hpts$bdry[[1]]$y, col="#4a007e50")

levelPlot <- levels(gr)[4]
levelPlot # this will plot Rhombifera
rowNums <- which(gr == levelPlot)
hpts<- convexhull.xy(x[rowNums,1:2])
hpts$bdry[[1]]$x
polygon(hpts$bdry[[1]]$x, hpts$bdry[[1]]$y, col="#80bfff50")

levelPlot <- levels(gr)[5]
levelPlot # this will plot Stylophora
rowNums <- which(gr == levelPlot)
hpts<- convexhull.xy(x[rowNums,1:2])
hpts$bdry[[1]]$x
polygon(hpts$bdry[[1]]$x, hpts$bdry[[1]]$y, col="#67d86850")

legend(locator(1), c("Blastoidea (n = 2)", "Cephalochordata (n = 1)", "Hemichordata

```

```
(n = 2)", "Rhombifera (n = 1)", "Stylophora (n = 3)", pch=c(19,19,19,19),
col=c("#f75d7c50", "#e9e92750", "#4a007e50", "#80bfff50", "#67d86850"), cex=0.7,
bty = "n")
```

```
# Biplot log
biplot(pca)
```

```
# LDA log: Group
lda <- lda(gr~ Length + Width + Depth + Spacing , data)
attach(lda)
prop.lda = lda$svd^2/sum(lda$svd^2) # proportions
print(prop.lda)
```

```
# predict LDA. It returns the classification and the posterior probabilities of the new
data based on the LD model:
plda <- predict (object = lda, newdata = data)# plot
```

```
plot(plda$x[,1], plda$x[,2], pch=19, col =hex, xlab="LD1 - 89.29%", ylab="LD2 -
8.79%") # make scatterplot
legend(locator(1), c("Balanoglossus sp.", "Branchiostoma floridae", "Cryptoschisma
sp.", "Jaekelocarpus oklahomensis", "Lagynocystis pyramidalis 2", "Lagynocystis
pyramidalis 1", "Schizocardium sp.", "Hyperoblastus reimanni", "Strobilocystites
sp."), pch=19, col=c("#ff9900", "#ff4646", "#ab59bc", "#6682ff", "#66ccff",
"#ff66cc", "#99ffcc", "#cc9900", "#33cc33"),cex=2/3, bty = "n")
text(plda$x[,1],plda$x[,2], labels=sp, col=hex, cex=0.5, pos=3)
```

```
# Plot Group
levelPlot <- levels(gr)[1]
levelPlot # this will plot Blastoidea
rowNums <- which(gr == levelPlot)
hpts<- convexhull.xy(plda$x[rowNums,1:2])
hpts$bdry[[1]]$x
polygon(hpts$bdry[[1]]$x, hpts$bdry[[1]]$y, col="#f75d7c50")
```

```
levelPlot <- levels(gr)[2]
levelPlot # this will plot Cephalochordate
rowNums <- which(gr == levelPlot)
hpts<- convexhull.xy(plda$x[rowNums,1:2])
hpts$bdry[[1]]$x
polygon(hpts$bdry[[1]]$x, hpts$bdry[[1]]$y, col="#e9e92750")
```

```
levelPlot <- levels(gr)[3]
levelPlot # this will plot Hemichordate
rowNums <- which(gr == levelPlot)
hpts<- convexhull.xy(plda$x[rowNums,1:2])
hpts$bdry[[1]]$x
polygon(hpts$bdry[[1]]$x, hpts$bdry[[1]]$y, col="#4a007e50")
```

```
levelPlot <- levels(gr)[4]
levelPlot # this will plot Rhombifera
```

```

rowNums <- which(gr == levelPlot)
hpts<- convexhull.xy(plda$x[rowNums,1:2])
hpts$bdry[[1]]$x
polygon(hpts$bdry[[1]]$x, hpts$bdry[[1]]$y, col="#80bfff50")

levelPlot <- levels(gr)[5]
levelPlot # this will plot Stylophora
rowNums <- which(gr == levelPlot)
hpts<- convexhull.xy(plda$x[rowNums,1:2])
hpts$bdry[[1]]$x
polygon(hpts$bdry[[1]]$x, hpts$bdry[[1]]$y, col="#67d86850")

legend(locator(1), c("Blastoidea (n = 2)", "Cephalochordata (n = 1)", "Hemichordata
(n = 2)", "Rhombifera (n = 1)", "Stylophora (n = 3)"), pch=c(19,19,19,19),
col=c("#f75d7c50", "#e9e92750", "#4a007e50", "#80bfff50", "#67d86850"), cex=0.7,
bty = "n")

# Plot Biplot for LDA log
heads <- coef(lda)
heads
biplot <- arrows(x0 = 0, y0 = 0, x1 = heads [,1], y1 = heads [,2], length = 1/10, col =
"cos2")
text(heads[,1:2], labels = row.names(heads))

# Error rates for LDA log
partimat(gr~., data=datalog, method="lda")

# MANOVA

len <- data$Length
wid <- data$Width
dep <- data$Depth
spa <- data$Spacing

spmanovas <- manova(cbind(len, wid, dep, spa) ~ sp)
summary(spmanovas)

grmanova <- manova(cbind(len, wid, dep, spa) ~ gr)
summary(grmanova)

summary.aov(spmanovas)
summary.aov(grmanova)

# ANOVA
# Length
aovlsp <- aov (len~sp, data = data)
pairwise.t.test(len, sp, p.adj = "none")
pairwise.t.test(len, sp, p.adj = "bonf") # Bonferroni
pairwise.t.test(len, sp, p.adj = "holm") # Holm

```

```
TukeyHSD(aovlsp) # Tukey comparisons of means 95% family-wise confidence level
```

```
aovlgr <- aov (len~gr, data = data)
pairwise.t.test(len, gr, p.adj = "none")
pairwise.t.test(len, gr, p.adj = "bonf") # Bonferroni
pairwise.t.test(len, gr, p.adj = "holm") # Holm
TukeyHSD(aovlgr) # Tukey comparisons of means 95% family-wise confidence level
```

```
# Width
```

```
aovwsp <- aov (wid~sp, data = data)
pairwise.t.test(wid, sp, p.adj = "none")
pairwise.t.test(wid, sp, p.adj = "bonf") # Bonferroni
pairwise.t.test(wid, sp, p.adj = "holm") # Holm
TukeyHSD(aovwsp) # Tukey comparisons of means 95% family-wise confidence
level
```

```
aovwgr <- aov (wid~gr, data = data)
pairwise.t.test(wid, gr, p.adj = "none")
pairwise.t.test(wid, gr, p.adj = "bonf") # Bonferroni
pairwise.t.test(wid, gr, p.adj = "holm") # Holm
TukeyHSD(aovwgr) # Tukey comparisons of means 95% family-wise confidence
level
```

```
# Depth
```

```
aovdsp <- aov (dep~sp, data = data)
pairwise.t.test(dep, sp, p.adj = "none")
pairwise.t.test(dep, sp, p.adj = "bonf") # Bonferroni
pairwise.t.test(dep, sp, p.adj = "holm") # Holm
TukeyHSD(aovdsp) # Tukey comparisons of means 95% family-wise confidence
level
```

```
aovdgr <- aov (dep~gr, data = data)
pairwise.t.test(dep, gr, p.adj = "none")
pairwise.t.test(dep, gr, p.adj = "bonf") # Bonferroni
pairwise.t.test(dep, gr, p.adj = "holm") # Holm
TukeyHSD(aovdgr) # Tukey comparisons of means 95% family-wise confidence
level
```

```
# Spacing
```

```
aovssp <- aov (spa~sp, data = data)
pairwise.t.test(spa, sp, p.adj = "none")
pairwise.t.test(spa, sp, p.adj = "bonf") # Bonferroni
pairwise.t.test(spa, sp, p.adj = "holm") # Holm
TukeyHSD(aovssp) # Tukey comparisons of means 95% family-wise confidence
level
```

```
aovsgr <- aov (spa~gr, data = data)
pairwise.t.test(spa, gr, p.adj = "none")
pairwise.t.test(spa, gr, p.adj = "bonf") # Bonferroni
pairwise.t.test(spa, gr, p.adj = "holm") # Holm
```

TukeyHSD(aovsgr) # Tukey comparisons of means 95% family-wise confidence level